

Report: Human-Centricity and the EU Core Values in EU Policy Documents

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Last updated: 2024.05.20

The aims: The goal of this report is to provide an overview of the EU core values and the human-centric approach as represented in EU policy documents.

The structure: The first two sections briefly present the notions of the EU core values and the human-centric approach. The subsequent sections cover the way these notions appear in six different EU policy documents.

The scope: “Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council: Laying Down Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence” (also known as the “EU AI Act”—(The European Commission, 2021a)), “Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area” (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education et al., 2015), “An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market” (The European Commission, 2022a), “Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe’s Recovery” (The European Commission, 2021b), “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market” (The European Commission, 2016), and “The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation” (The European Commission, 2024).

The findings: The analysed documents vary in their treatment of value concepts, with some only bearing indirect relevance to EU core values and others covering ethical issues relevant to standardisation in a more explicit manner (e.g., the “EU AI Act” and “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market”). In general, the policy documents encompass a relatively broad range of values including safety, security, privacy, autonomy, transparency, accountability, fairness, and non-discrimination, alongside some explicit references to fundamental rights central to EU policies. Given the growing need for ethics in the EU’s standardisation landscape (as is evident from the document analysis), incorporating ethical knowledge and skills into standardisation education may be essential to prepare the future professionals for addressing the emerging challenges in a way that goes in line with EU values and policies.

1. What are the EU Core Values?

According to the official EU webpage (Directorate-General for Communication, n.d.), the EU is founded on the following values:

1. **Human dignity:** Human dignity is inviolable. It must be respected, protected and constitutes the real basis of fundamental rights.¹
2. **Freedom:** Freedom of movement gives citizens the right to move and reside freely within the Union. Individual freedoms such as respect for private life, freedom of thought, religion, assembly, expression and information are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.
3. **Democracy:** The functioning of the EU is founded on representative democracy. A European citizen automatically enjoys political rights. Every adult EU citizen has the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in elections to the European Parliament. EU citizens have the right to stand as a candidate and to vote in their country of residence, or in their country of origin.
4. **Equality:** Equality is about equal rights for all citizens before the law. The principle of equality between women and men underpins all European policies and is the basis for European integration. It applies in all areas. The principle of equal pay for equal work became part of the Treaty of Rome in 1957.
5. **Rule of law:** The EU is based on the rule of law. Everything the EU does is founded on treaties, voluntarily and democratically agreed by its EU countries. Law and justice are upheld by an independent judiciary. The EU countries gave final jurisdiction to the European Court of Justice—its judgments have to be respected by all.
6. **Human rights:** Human rights are protected by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. These cover the right to be free from discrimination on the basis of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation, the right to the protection of your personal data, and the right to get access to justice.

2. What is the Human-Centric Approach?

The concept of “human-centricity” is closely tied to the values listed above but is also distinct from them. While the core values—such as human rights, democracy, and equality—are typically conceived as central to the EU’s human-centric approach, the notion of human-centricity is more commonly deployed in the context of digital development and policies. In general, the goal of the human-centric approach is to “foster inclusive digital economies and societies in which all citizens—notably women and young people—have equal opportunities to participate in the digital world. The human-centric approach puts people at the heart of the digital transformation—driven by people’s

¹ In ethics, there is no universally accepted account of what human dignity consists in—it is a contested notion. However, in the context of EU policymaking, it generally refers to “the inherent worth and value of every individual, regardless of their background, status, or circumstances. It entails the recognition and respect for each person’s autonomy, integrity, and inherent rights. This includes the right to be treated with fairness, equality, and respect, as well as protection from degrading treatment or exploitation” (generated by GPT-3.5 under specific instructions).

needs, fundamental rights and intersectional challenges to closing digital divides” (*D4D Hub Principles*, 2024).

While in its core the approach is concerned with policies, strategies, and initiatives that foster the fundamental rights and welfare of people, various sources (*Demystifying the People-Centred Approach for the Digital Transformation*, 2023; The European Commission, n.d., 2022b, 2023) seem to converge on several particular values (or groups thereof) that consistently appear in the context of human-centricity in various information sources on the EU policies. One could summarize them in the following way:

1. **Empowerment, social inclusion, and solidarity:** Empowering people by ensuring that they get to fully enjoy the opportunities created by digital transformation, with an emphasis on the needs of elderly people, people living in rural areas, persons with disabilities, marginalized, vulnerable, or disenfranchised people, etc., tackling digital divides.
2. **Safety and security:** Ensuring safe and secure digital products, services, and technologies for everyone, protecting people’s privacy, combating various forms of harmful content (e.g., disinformation and manipulation), including harassment and gender-based violence.
3. **Freedom, trust, and transparency:** Empowering people to make free and informed choices online based on objective and reliable information, promoting trustworthy and transparent AI systems.
4. **Participation and democracy:** Using emerging technologies to stimulate engagement and democratic participation, enabling access to trustworthy, diverse, and multilingual online environment, promoting transparency in online services, taking into consideration our cultural and linguistic diversity.
5. **Sustainability:** Minimizing the negative environmental and societal impact of digital technologies and services and ensuring the availability of information on their impact and energy consumption.

3. Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council: Laying Down Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence

The document that is called “Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council: Laying Down Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence” (The European Commission, 2021a)—also known as the “EU AI Act”—is the EU’s first legal framework that puts forward harmonized rules for the development, use, and market regulation of artificial intelligence (AI). It categorizes AI applications into (1) low or minimal risk, (2) high risk, and (3) unacceptable risk. While the first group of AI applications is left largely unregulated and the third is outright banned, the second—

high-risk applications—is subject to specific legal regulations and is the key focus of the act. The overarching goal behind the act proposal seems to be “to ensure that Europeans can benefit from new technologies developed and functioning according to Union values, fundamental rights and principles”² (The European Commission, 2021a subsec. 1.1.).³ As such, the act is strongly undergirded by ethical considerations, including EU values and fundamental rights (ibid.).

Although the act proposal undoubtedly has an ethical basis at the fundamental level, ethics as such is not the primary focus of its contents, given that it’s first and foremost a legal document. Therefore, it may be important to distinguish between different ways how ethical considerations manifest in it. Here one could distinguish between parts of the act (e.g., articles or paragraphs) that (1) are more administrative/bureaucratic and only indirectly pertain to ethical commitments (covered in 3.1.), (2) those that explicitly mention general ethical concepts (e.g., “values” or “rights”) (covered in 3.2.), and (3) those that mention more specific ethical concepts (e.g., “right to life” as opposed to “fundamental right”) (covered in 3.3.). Although most parts of the act fall under the first category, some other parts explicitly refer to values and/or rights and therefore fall under the second category. Subsection 3.5., titled “Fundamental Rights,” is one of the few parts that belongs to the third category. The mentioned subsection serves as a reference point for the notion of fundamental rights, which is occasionally mentioned in the act. Below, one can find a set of examples from the act that contain ethical concepts to varying degrees and a brief commentary that is provided for each example.

3.1. Examples of implicit ethical commitments

Example – #1:

Article 48: *EU declaration of conformity*

1. The provider shall draw up a written EU declaration of conformity for each AI system and keep it at the disposal of the national competent authorities for 10 years after the AI system has been placed on the market or put into service. The EU declaration of conformity shall identify the AI system for which it has been drawn up. A copy of the EU declaration of conformity shall be given to the relevant national competent authorities upon request.

² In general terms, a value is a good and desirable aspect that ought to be promoted in a particular context. A principle, on the other hand, serves as an expression of a particular value in the form of a fundamental rule that is meant to guide one’s behavior and decision-making. In this particular case, the phrase “values, fundamental rights, and principles” could be construed as a reference to a general set of ideals and doctrines that shape the EU’s objectives and actions.

³ More specifically, the Commission (ibid.) state the following objectives:

- Ensure that AI systems placed on the Union market and used are safe and respect existing law on fundamental rights and Union values;
- Ensure legal certainty to facilitate investment and innovation in AI;
- Enhance governance and effective enforcement of existing law on fundamental rights and safety requirements applicable to AI systems;
- Facilitate the development of a single market for lawful, safe and trustworthy AI applications and prevent market fragmentation.

2. The EU declaration of conformity shall state that the high-risk AI system in question meets the requirements set out in Chapter 2 of this Title. The EU declaration of conformity shall contain the information set out in Annex V and shall be translated into an official Union language or languages required by the Member State(s) in which the high-risk AI system is made available.
3. Where high-risk AI systems are subject to other Union harmonisation legislation which also requires an EU declaration of conformity, a single EU declaration of conformity shall be drawn up in respect of all Union legislations applicable to the high-risk AI system. The declaration shall contain all the information required for identification of the Union harmonisation legislation to which the declaration relates.
4. By drawing up the EU declaration of conformity, the provider shall assume responsibility for compliance with the requirements set out in Chapter 2 of this Title. The provider shall keep the EU declaration of conformity up-to-date as appropriate.
5. The Commission shall be empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 73 for the purpose of updating the content of the EU declaration of conformity set out in Annex V in order to introduce elements that become necessary in light of technical progress.

Comments: Article 48 requires that providers draw up a written EU declaration of conformity for each AI system placed on the market or put into service and present additional regulations concerning the mentioned declaration. Most of the articles in the act are similar to this one in the sense that they appear more administrative and bureaucratic rather than ethically significant. However, one could argue that there is still a connection between them and the EU's human-centric values. For example, a case could be made that detailed regulations of this sort with respect to high-risk AI systems ensure transparency regarding the AI systems' compliance with regulatory requirements and promote accountability, oversight, responsibility, and consumer protection all of which are important values in the development and utilization of AI systems.⁴

Example – #2:

Article 22: Duty of information

Where the high-risk AI system presents a risk within the meaning of Article 65(1) and that risk is known to the provider of the system, that provider shall immediately inform the national competent authorities of the Member States in which it made the system available and, where applicable, the

⁴ From the standpoint of standardisation, the significance here is that if one demands standards makers to make conformity statements or other public-oriented declarations to allow the consumers of standards to know what the standards are about, that makes the standardisation more "human-centric" in the sense that the process promotes a particular value espoused by the EU.

notified body that issued a certificate for the high-risk AI system, in particular of the non-compliance and of any corrective actions taken.

Comments: Similar to the first example, the above part of the act is not explicitly engaged in ethical considerations either. However, the duty of information for providers of high-risk AI systems could still be seen as relevant with respect to EU values in the sense that it pertains to risk management and consumer protection (e.g., disclosing the risks involved), transparency and oversight, as well as enabling corrective actions and quality management. Regulations of this sort add to the overall safety and security of AI systems and foster transparency and accountability in their deployment. Most chapters and articles in the act relate to ethics and European values in a way similar to the two examples presented so far.

3.2. Examples of general ethical concepts

The following examples, while distinct, are listed under the same heading, given their overall respective similarities. The relevant terms are emphasized.

List of examples – #3:

Act proposal, paragraph 5 (excerpt): By laying down those rules, this Regulation supports the objective of the Union of being a global leader in the development of **secure, trustworthy and ethical artificial intelligence**, as stated by the European Council, and **it ensures the protection of ethical principles** [unspecified in the document], as specifically requested by the European Parliament.

Act proposal, paragraph 10: **In order to ensure a level playing field and an effective protection of rights and freedoms of individuals across the Union**, the rules established by this Regulation should apply to providers of AI systems in a **non-discriminatory** manner, irrespective of whether they are established within the Union or in a third country, and to users of AI systems established within the Union.

Act proposal, paragraph 27 (excerpt): High-risk AI systems should only be placed on the Union market or put into service if they comply with certain mandatory requirements... **AI systems identified as high-risk should be limited to those that have a significant harmful impact on the health, safety and fundamental rights** of persons in the Union and such limitation minimises any potential restriction to international trade, if any.

Act proposal, paragraph 43: Requirements should apply to high-risk AI systems as regards the quality of data sets used, technical documentation and record-keeping, transparency and the provision of information to users, human oversight, and robustness, accuracy and cybersecurity. **Those requirements are necessary to effectively mitigate the risks for health, safety and fundamental rights**, as applicable in the light of the intended purpose of the system, and no other less trade restrictive measures are reasonably available, thus avoiding unjustified restrictions to trade.

Article 14 (*Human oversight*), paragraph 2: **Human oversight shall aim at preventing or minimising the risks to health, safety or fundamental rights** that may emerge when a high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose or under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse, in particular when such risks persist notwithstanding the application of other requirements set out in this Chapter.

Article 41 (*Common specifications*), paragraph 1 (excerpt): Where harmonised standards referred to in Article 40 do not exist or where the Commission considers that the relevant harmonised standards are insufficient **or that there is a need to address specific safety or fundamental right concerns**, the Commission may, by means of implementing acts, adopt common specifications in respect of the requirements set out in Chapter 2 of this Title...

Article 53 (*AI regulatory sandboxes*), paragraph 3: The AI regulatory sandboxes shall not affect the supervisory and corrective powers of the competent authorities. **Any significant risks to health and safety and fundamental rights identified during the development and testing of such systems shall result in immediate mitigation** and, failing that, in the suspension of the development and testing process until such mitigation takes place.

Article 62 (*Reporting of serious incidents and of malfunctioning*), paragraph 1 (excerpt): Providers of high-risk AI systems placed on the Union market **shall report any serious incident or any malfunctioning of those systems which constitutes a breach of obligations under Union law intended to protect fundamental rights** to the market surveillance authorities of the Member States where that incident or breach occurred.

Comments: While many parts of the act are only “indirectly” ethical, there are some that explicitly mention general ethical concepts, such as “fundamental rights” or “Union values.” Several examples of such cases are listed above. Although the strong presence of these concepts in the act indicates a high degree of commitment to fundamental moral values on behalf of the Commission, the concepts

themselves are rather abstract and lack specificity. Thus, while their presence is worth noting, it is important to clarify their meaning in the document. This is where Subsection 3.5. of the act becomes particularly relevant. Its significance is explained below.

3.3. Examples of specific ethical concepts

Subsection 3.5. in the act, titled “Fundamental rights,” offers a more specific list of rights that, according to the Commission, may be adversely affected by AI systems (e.g., due to their opacity, complexity, dependency on data, and autonomy). In general, the mentioned subsection of the act proposal could be seen as a reference point for the general ethical concepts mentioned earlier. In other words, although numerous parts of the act stress the importance of “fundamental rights” without elaborating on their exact content, Subsection 3.5. gives one a more specific idea of what this content may be. Consider the following example:

Example – #4:

Act proposal, Subsection 3.5. *Fundamental rights* (excerpt)

The use of AI with its specific characteristics (e.g. opacity, complexity, dependency on data, autonomous behaviour) can adversely affect a number of fundamental rights enshrined in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. This proposal seeks to ensure a high level of protection for those fundamental rights and aims to address various sources of risks through a clearly defined risk-based approach. With a set of requirements for trustworthy AI and proportionate obligations on all value chain participants, the proposal will enhance and promote the protection of the rights protected by the Charter: the right to human dignity (Article 1), respect for private life and protection of personal data (Articles 7 and 8), non-discrimination (Article 21) and equality between women and men (Article 23). It aims to prevent a chilling effect on the rights to freedom of expression (Article 11) and freedom of assembly (Article 12), to ensure protection of the right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial, the rights of defence and the presumption of innocence (Articles 47 and 48), as well as the general principle of good administration. Furthermore, as applicable in certain domains, the proposal will positively affect the rights of a number of special groups, such as the workers’ rights to fair and just working conditions (Article 31), a high level of consumer protection (Article 28), the rights of the child (Article 24) and the integration of persons with disabilities (Article 26). The right to a high level of environmental protection and the improvement of the quality of the environment (Article 37) is also relevant, including in relation to the health and safety of people. The obligations for ex ante testing, risk management and human oversight will also facilitate the respect of other fundamental rights by minimising the risk of erroneous or biased AI-assisted decisions in critical areas such as education and training, employment, important services, law enforcement and the judiciary. In case

infringements of fundamental rights still happen, effective redress for affected persons will be made possible by ensuring transparency and traceability of the AI systems coupled with strong ex post controls.

This proposal imposes some restrictions on the freedom to conduct business (Article 16) and the freedom of art and science (Article 13) to ensure compliance with overriding reasons of public interest such as health, safety, consumer protection and the protection of other fundamental rights (“responsible innovation”) when high-risk AI technology is developed and used. Those restrictions are proportionate and limited to the minimum necessary to prevent and mitigate serious safety risks and likely infringements of fundamental rights.

Comments: In general, Subsection 3.5. provides a fairly comprehensive list of specific rights that ought to be taken into account in moral and legal decision making concerning the development and use of AI systems. Additionally, the Commission recognizes the possibility that the protection of fundamental rights may necessitate imposing restrictions on certain freedoms, such as the freedom to conduct business and the freedom of art and science. Specifying the fundamental rights and acknowledging them as “overriding reasons” in relation to certain freedoms underlines the Union’s commitment to promote responsible innovation and protect the interests and welfare of individuals and society in an appropriate manner. Moreover, although the excerpt above does not elaborate on the rights mentioned in detail, it makes a reference to the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, which contains concise descriptions of what EU considers to be fundamental (human) rights (*Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union*, 2012). These rights are in line with the EU’s core values outlined at the beginning of this document.

3.4. Final remarks

Without any doubt, the EU AI Act has strong ethical underpinnings, which are represented in the document in a relatively clear and rigorous manner. The need to consider concerns related to health, safety, and fundamental rights is stressed consistently in different parts of the act, whereas Subsection 3.5. provides a more specific outline of what the fundamental rights in question are and additionally refers to the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, effectively serving as the ethical backbone of the act. While most chapters and articles in the act do not contain explicit ethical considerations and concepts, they can still be construed as ethically significant and necessary in promoting and safeguarding the values of transparency, accountability, oversight, risk management, consumer protection, right to good administration, and others. These values can be seen as more specific aspects of various fundamental rights such as the rights to liberty, security, privacy, and information. As far as other relevant topics go, the act does not cover digital skills or gender-related issues in detail.

Digital skills are not mentioned, whereas gender equality is mentioned once as consistent with the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (The European Commission, 2021a subsec. 1.2.).

4. Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area

The “Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG)” (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education et al., 2015) is one of the key documents in European higher education. It provides a common quality assurance framework for higher education institutions in the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

The primary focus of ESG is quality assurance in higher education, which, as emphasized in the document itself, is highly important for social cohesion, economic growth, global competitiveness, and cultural development (p. 4). While all of these aspects have ethical implications, their connection to ethics is not straightforward, and the contents of the document do not directly pertain to ethics. Nevertheless, some of the values of the Union manifest themselves in ESG in a more indirect manner and could be presented as follows:

- **Transparency, accountability, and responsibility:** according to ESG, all internal stakeholders assume responsibility for fostering quality culture in higher education institutions (p. 8). The document also emphasizes the importance of transparency in the implementation of access policies, admission processes, and criteria (p. 10), as well as in the recruitment and development of the staff (p. 11). Additionally, it stresses the need for reports from external experts and agencies to ensure quality assurance and requires that the reports be published, clear, and accessible (p. 16); also, that the agencies involved have full responsibility for their operations (p. 18) and are accountable to their stakeholders (p. 20).
- **Fairness, non-discrimination, and inclusion:** the document states that quality assurance policies should guard the students and the staff against any kind of intolerance or discrimination (pp. 8, 20). Moreover, according to ESG, student-centred learning and teaching must respect the diversity of students (pp. 9, 11) (e.g., mature, part-time employed, and international students, as well as students with disabilities) and ensure that the student admission, progression, recognition, and certification processes (p. 10)—as well as the recruitment and development of the staff (p. 11)—are fair.
- **Trust and respect:** ESG promote mutual respect between teachers and learners (p. 9) and seek to build trust within European higher education systems and institutions (pp. 4, 5) as well as between institutions, the public, and agencies (p. 18).

In sum, although the primary focus of ESG is the effectiveness and quality of study programs, there are a few parts in the document that indicate commitment to the values endorsed by the Union.

5. An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market

“An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market” (The European Commission, 2022a) is an initiative aimed at creating a robust standardisation framework that enhances EU’s global competitiveness, resilience, and sustainability. It is strategically oriented toward green and digital transitions, interoperability, the position of the EU in the global arena, and the EU single market, stressing the importance of standards and the role of standardisation experts in these areas.

While the document does mention EU values in several parts, it does so only in a rather general and vague manner, using the term “EU values” rather than referring to something more specific. In the main text of the document, values are mentioned in the following general way as presented in the examples below:

1. “Europe’s competitiveness, technological sovereignty, ability to reduce dependencies and protection of EU values, including our social and environmental ambitions, will depend on how successful European actors are in standardisation at international level” (p. 1).
2. “To ensure that the European standardisation system delivers in this respect, measures should be taken to ensure that it promotes EU interests and values” (p. 2).
3. “The EU and its Member States must promote a more strategic approach to international standardisation activities ... in order to ensure the EU’s global competitiveness, security and open strategic autonomy, as well as the ability of the EU to promote its values” (pp. 5–6).
4. “With this strategy, the Commission underpins the EU’s role as a global frontrunner in the development of standards, supporting EU values and providing industries with a competitive edge” (p. 10).

However, it is noteworthy that there are two instances of more specific values in the document as well namely, democratic values:

5. “More than ever, standards do not only have to deal with technical components, but also incorporate core EU democratic values and interests, as well as green and social principles” (p. 4).

6. “Therefore, the Commission is committed to making the European standardisation system more functional and agile, to deliver on the standards that make our industries more competitive, serve the EU’s public interest, promote sustainability, and preserve and reinforce democratic values” (p. 9).

In sum, “The EU Strategy on Standardisation” makes several general mentions of EU values and two of democratic values in particular. While the document is not strongly focused on value questions, it is important to pay attention to the context in which they appear. Virtually all of the examples presented above stress the importance of standardisation in safeguarding and reinforcing core EU values in general and democratic values in particular. This implies that value questions are expected to play a role in the context of the EU’s strategy on standardisation.

6. Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe’s Recovery

“Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe’s Recovery” (The European Commission, 2021b) is a strategic initiative by the EU that was put forward in response to the aftermaths of the COVID-19 crisis, aiming to boost Europe’s recovery, support the twin transitions (green and digital), and secure Europe’s Single Market. Its proposals include measures to strengthen the resilience of Single Market, address dependencies in key sectors and promote autonomy, accelerate the twin transitions, and regulate foreign subsidies, among others.

While the document is strongly focused on means of enhancing Europe’s economic recovery and resilience, it does not explicitly engage with value questions or ethical considerations. There are a few statements that stress the importance of notions like equality and fairness in the context of European economy such as the following: “The Commission is paying a particular attention to equal rights and opportunities for an inclusive recovery across all sectors” (p. 2). Nevertheless, such statements only appear “in passing” and are not elaborated on. As a result, the document offers little substance with respect to value questions.

7. ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market

“ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market” (The European Commission, 2016) is a communication issued by the European Commission that outlines the standardisation priorities in the context of ICT and EU’s Digital Single Market. It emphasizes the opportunities presented by digital technologies, the importance of framework for innovation, fair competition, and cooperation among businesses, the interconnection between the green and digital transitions, and European values in the context of digital solutions, among other things. The document stresses the importance of

harmonized standards within the Union for the deployment of technologies such as cloud computing, Internet of Things (IoT), 5G networks, data infrastructures, eHealth, automated vehicles, and more.

Although this communication document does not mention the EU’s human-centric approach by name, it draws considerably on its main values. For example, it calls for “transparency, openness, impartiality and consensus” (p. 4) in ICT standardisation and repeatedly stresses the importance of respect for privacy (e.g., private data protection) (pp. 3, 6, 7, 9), safety, security, and reliability of digital technologies (pp. 6–12), as well as interoperability (pp. 2, 6–12). The notions of trust (pp. 6–8, 10) and transparency (pp. 4, 6, 10, 14), which are both part of EU’s human-centric approach, are mentioned quite frequently as well (e.g., in the context of data management). Moreover, the Commission emphasizes the importance of fairness and non-discrimination in ICT standardisation (pp. 11, 13)—particularly in the context of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and licensing terms—stressing the need for “a fair return on investment for standard essential patent (SEPs) holders and fair access to SEPs for all players—and especially SMEs ...” (p. 13).

Finally, the document draws attention to the importance of fundamental rights for the development of ICT standards and, on page 4, makes an explicit reference to the Charter of Fundamental Rights. Consider the following passage:

The actions to address the [new] challenges [in the development of ICT standards] needs [sic] to ensure a proper balancing in view of their compliance with fundamental rights, as standardisation may have implications in this area. For instance, the actions need to ensure full respect of the rights to private life and personal data protection, and should also take into account other **fundamental rights** [emphasis in the original], including freedom to provide business and right to property. (pp. 3–4)

In sum, the “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market” communication document embodies the EU’s human-centric approach by drawing on values such as transparency, privacy protection, safety, security, reliability, interoperability, trust, and fairness. It calls for a responsible and value-sensitive approach to ICT standardisation, seeking to address new challenges in a way that complies with fundamental rights.

8. The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation

“The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation” (The European Commission, 2024) is a document published by the European Commission that identifies strategic policy priorities and actions for European standardisation. In total, it sets out 72 specific courses of action that would implement the mentioned priorities through the development and revision of

standards in the context of European industry resilience, the digital transition, the green transition, and the internal market for services and products.

Since the document is focused on proposing specific actions that contribute to achieving European standardisation goals, it does not engage with ethical issues to a great extent. However, for each of the 72 proposed actions the Commission identifies specific objectives under the heading “Specific objectives and policies for European standards/European standardisation deliverables” (p. 5). In this column of objectives and policies, one can find some references to EU core values in relation to specific areas of standardisation. The areas and their respective values are listed below:

- **Standardisation actions/deliverables supporting the resilience of European industry (pp. 5–6):** this part of the document covers issues such as critical raw materials, additive manufacturing techniques, bio-materials, bio-based, and wood-derived products, as well as advanced materials. With respect to EU values, it repeatedly stresses the importance of sustainability in relation to production and manufacturing and mentions safety with respect to advanced materials.
- **Standardisation actions/deliverables supporting the digital transition (pp. 6–9):** this part covers issues such as cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements, quantum technologies, EU trusted data framework, virtual and augmented reality ecosystem and economy, harmonization of barcodes, and AI. Here, safety and security are constantly stressed as critical elements for standardisation of different kinds of digital technologies. This part also emphasizes the importance of interoperability⁵ (regarding numerous technologies), privacy and autonomy (e.g., data protection and access), and trust (e.g., among vendors, customers, and service providers). In relation to standardisation of AI, the Commission explicitly calls for respect for fundamental values and human rights.
- **Standardisation actions/deliverables supporting the green transition (pp. 10–23):** this is the longest part in the action plan, proposing a total of 42 actions to promote green transition. It includes standardisation activities with respect to issues such as hydrogen technologies, electricity grids, ecodesign and labelling of light sources, ecodesign and labelling of water heaters, climate resilience infrastructure, microplastic, assessment of ecosystem services, and many others. While this part pays considerable attention to environmental issues (e.g., energy consumption, air quality, greenhouse gas emissions, microplastic releases into the

⁵ Strictly speaking, interoperability may not be an ethical value. However, it facilitates various valuable aspects of technologies, enabling users to have greater freedom (e.g., allowing them to switch providers without being locked into proprietary systems), promoting fair competition by preventing monopolistic practices, providing users with greater control over their data, promoting inclusion and accessibility, and more.

environment, biodiversity loss, soil contamination, and so forth), core values that are not related to environmental sustainability are virtually absent in it.

- **Standardisation actions/deliverables supporting the internal market for services and products (pp. 23–27):** this part covers issues such as medical devices, weighing and measuring instruments, interoperability of the rail system, electromagnetic compatibility, radio equipment, consumer products safety standards, and others. In this part, safety is mentioned in most of the proposed standardisation areas that concern services and products for the internal market with few mentions of other values. Environmental protection, consumer protection, and fair trading are mentioned in relation to standardisation of weighing and measurement instruments.

In sum, the Commission stresses the importance of safety in relation to numerous standardisation areas within the categories of digital transition and the internal market for services and products. Environmental sustainability is the central focus of standards for the green transition, whereas standards supporting the resilience of European industry must account for sustainability more generally. The most diverse value concepts appear in the context of digital standardisation and AI in particular, including requirements for safety, privacy, autonomy, trust, interoperability, and respect for fundamental values and rights.

9. Concluding Remarks and Implications for Standardisation Education

In sum, the presence of value concepts in the analysed documents varies considerably as does their degree of specificity. For example, the strategic initiative “Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe’s Recovery” makes few mentions of EU core values altogether, whereas “The EU Strategy on Standardisation” cases refers to “EU values” in a few cases but without specifying them, except for democratic values which are emphasized more strongly. Similarly, the “Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area” contains parts that indicate commitment to some of the core EU values—such as fairness, non-discrimination, and transparency—but only in a more implicit manner, with few direct mentions of the values themselves.

The other three analysed documents—“The EU AI Act,” “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market,” and “The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation”—are more explicit on ethical issues relevant to standardisation. Not only do their contents embody a diverse set of values (e.g., safety and security, privacy and autonomy, transparency, accountability, fairness, and non-discrimination, among others) and a human-centric approach to emerging technologies, but the mentioned documents also make explicit references to

the notion of fundamental rights, which is at the heart of both ethics and EU policies. While “The EU AI Act” and “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market” call for respect for fundamental rights in the context of digital technologies and AI, “The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation,” specifically stresses the need for standardisation professionals to take fundamental rights into consideration in relation to AI, underscoring the importance of ethics in this context.

Based on the findings of this report and on the current state of emerging socially disruptive technologies, such as AI, it is evident that the EU’s standardisation landscape is increasingly becoming intertwined with ethics and requires additional ethical expertise to address new challenges. This expertise presupposes knowledge and skills in the fields of technology ethics (e.g., AI ethics) and business ethics, as well as understanding key ethical notions that are commonly present in EU policy documents relevant to standardisation, including fundamental/human rights, moral values, justice, fairness, wellbeing, non-discrimination, inclusion, (un)acceptable risk, and others. Although this report may not warrant drawing strong conclusions regarding the place of ethics in standardisation curriculum, understanding the ethical dimensions of digitalization, business practices, cultural differences, and sustainability initiatives seems essential for preparing students to navigate the diverse and interdisciplinary challenges that come with the professional practice of responsible and value-sensitive standardisation propagated by the EU.

Bibliography

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. (2012). Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT>

D4D Hub Principles. (2024). Digital for Development (D4D) Hub. <https://d4dhub.eu>

Demystifying the People-Centred Approach for the Digital Transformation. (2023). CONCORD. https://concordeurope.org/?sdm_process_download=1&download_id=25335

Directorate-General for Communication. (n.d.). *Aims and Values*. European Union. https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/principles-and-values/aims-and-values_en

European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education, European Students’ Union, European University Association, European Association of Institutions in Higher Education, Education International, BUSINESSEUROPE, & European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education. (2015). *Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG)*. EHEA. https://ehea.info/media.ehea.info/file/2015_Yerevan/72/7/European_Standards_and_Guidelines_for_Quality_Assurance_in_the_EHEA_2015_MC_613727.pdf

The European Commission. (n.d.). *Responsible Digitalisation*. European Commission. <https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/digital-and-infrastructure/responsible->

Appendix 1: Value concepts in “The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union”

	Concepts	Definitions and Sources
1.	Democracy	<p>“Democracy” refers very generally to a method of collective decision making characterized by a kind of equality among the participants at an essential stage of the decision-making process. The most important element of democracy as a form of government is self-rule, equally distributed among the people. Other noteworthy elements include respect for minority rights, rule of law, protection of human rights, and mechanisms for accountability and participation.</p> <p>Sources: Democracy (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy); Democracy: Definition and Explanation (politicalsciencenotes.com)</p>
2.	Dignity	<p>“Dignity” is a complex and contested concept that, in general terms, refers to absolute, intrinsic, and unconditional value. It is a sense of self-worth, which we have a duty to develop and respect in ourselves and a duty to protect in others. The concept of human dignity features in ethical, legal, and political discourse as a foundational commitment to human value or human status, but the source of that value, or the nature of that status, are contested.</p> <p>Sources: What is dignity? - Ethics Explainer by The Ethics Centre; How to define dignity and its place in human rights – a philosopher’s view (theconversation.com); Human Dignity Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy (utm.edu)</p>
3.	Equality	<p>“Equality” is a contested concept that signifies correspondence between a group of different objects, persons, processes, or circumstances that have the same qualities in at least one respect, but not all respects, i.e., regarding one specific feature, with differences in other features. “Equality” can be used in the very same sense both to describe (e.g., when two people are said to have the same weight) and prescribe (e.g., when it is said people ought to be equal before the law). The fundamental idea between the widely accepted principle of human equality is that human beings, despite their differences, are to be regarded as one another’s equals in terms of their worth, dignity, and respect they deserve.</p> <p>Source: Equality (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</p>
4.	Ethical principles	<p>In the context of ethics, principles refer to fundamental guidelines that help determine what acts are morally right or wrong. While they do not offer a straightforward formula for determining the right course of action, they provide essential considerations to weigh when faced with ethical dilemmas. Ethical principles prescribe actions that promote certain moral values such as autonomy, beneficence, nonmaleficence, and justice. Principles that are highly specific are typically referred to as rules.</p> <p>Sources: Exploring Ethics: Understanding the History, Theories, and Applications of Moral Principles (eresearch-ethics.org); What is Ethical principles - Meaning and definition - Pallipedia; Beauchamp, T., and J.</p>

	Concepts	Definitions and Sources
		F. Childress. 2001. <i>Principles of Biomedical Ethics</i> (5th ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.
5.	Freedom	<p>Freedom (or liberty) in a general sense refers to the quality or state of being free: the absence of necessity, coercion, or constraint in choice or action. Negative freedom is the absence of obstacles, barriers or constraints. One has negative freedom to the extent that actions are available to one in this negative sense. Positive freedom is the possibility of acting—or the fact of acting—in such a way as to take control of one’s life and realize one’s fundamental purposes.</p> <p>Sources: Freedom Definition & Meaning - Merriam-Webster; Positive and Negative Liberty (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</p>
6.	Justice	<p>Justice is the ethical, philosophical idea that people are to be treated impartially, fairly, properly, and reasonably by the law and by arbiters of the law, that laws are to ensure that no harm befalls another, and that, where harm is alleged, a remedial action is taken—both the accuser and the accused receive a morally right consequence merited by their actions. In ethics, the concept of justice is closely related to that of “rightness” or morality in general, but particularly in the sense of morality in the sense of “what we owe to each other.”</p> <p>Sources: justice Wex US Law LII / Legal Information Institute (cornell.edu); Justice (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</p>
7.	Moral duties	<p>In its most fundamental sense, a moral duty or obligation refers to a moral requirement to follow a certain course of action, that is, to do, or refrain from doing, certain things. It is not tied to any legal requirement, whether perfect or imperfect, nor is it connected to receiving any material or pecuniary benefit. Moral duty springs from a sense of justice and equity that an honourable person would have, and not from a mere sense of doing benevolence or charity.</p> <p>Sources: Introduction to Ethical Concepts, Part 2 (mit.edu); Moral Obligation Law and Legal Definition USLegal, Inc.</p>
8.	Morality	<p>At the most minimal, morality is a set of norms and principles that govern our actions with respect to each other and which are taken to have a special kind of weight or authority. More fundamentally, we can also think of morality as consisting of moral reasons, either grounded in some more basic value, or, the other way around, grounding value.</p> <p>Source: Moral Theory (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</p>
9.	Rights (fundamental rights, human rights)	<p>Rights are entitlements (not) to perform certain actions, or (not) to be in certain states; or entitlements that others (not) perform certain actions or (not) be in certain states. To accept a set of rights is to approve a distribution of freedom and authority, and so to endorse a certain view of what may, must, and must not be done. Rights correlate with duties: if someone has a right, then others have a corresponding duty toward the right-bearer. Moral rights are commonly distinguished from legal and customary rights, with moral rights being grounded in moral reasons, legal rights deriving from the laws of the society, and customary rights existing by local convention.</p>

	Concepts	Definitions and Sources
		<p>Source: Rights (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</p> <p>Human rights are primarily moral rights of high priority that are universally valid, independent of any legal recognition by particular nation-states or of particular times and places. All human beings are endowed with these rights simply by virtue of their humanity. In this respect, human rights are commonly seen as inborn, unalterable and inalienable. In addition, they are considered the minimal standards necessary to protect the most vital and precious interests and values of human beings—for example, their freedom, safety, equality, political participation and social security, to name just a few.</p> <p>Source: Gordon, J.-S. 2015. “Human Rights and Cultural Identity.” <i>Baltic Journal of Law & Politics</i> 8(2): 112–135. (see pages 114–115)</p> <p>Fundamental rights, according to the EU, largely refer to the same substance as human rights. They are the rights of people in the EU as enshrined in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, which contains rights and freedoms grouped under six titles: dignity, freedoms, equality, solidarity, citizens’ rights and justice. In a more general ethical sense, fundamental rights can be seen as basic moral rights of high priority that subsume but are not limited to human rights.</p> <p>Sources: What are fundamental rights? European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (europa.eu); Why do we need the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights? (europa.eu); Gordon, J-S. 2023. <i>The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Human Rights Legislation</i>. Palgrave Macmillan. (see § 5.3)</p>
10.	Solidarity	<p>Since the early- to late-nineteenth century, when the term “solidarity” became prevalent, it has always been used to describe a special relationship of unity and mutual indebtedness within a group. In social and political philosophy, the concept of solidarity is primarily used to evaluate, guide, and describe activities within groups and between individuals and groups. The concept of solidarity has been invoked with increasing regularity in contemporary social movements (Movement for Black Lives, Occupy, MeToo, climate change activism), law and politics (COVID, EU, constitutions around the world, human rights), and even bioethics.</p> <p>Source: Solidarity in Social and Political Philosophy (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy/Summer 2023 Edition)</p>

	Concepts	Definitions and Sources
11.	Values (universal values)	<p>In the most abstract sense, values refer to valuable and desirable aspects or qualities of something that motivate one’s action. Values and disvalues are expressed through certain evaluative concepts, such as “good” and “bad”, “better” and “worse,” “right” and “wrong,” “just” and “unjust,” and so forth. Personal values are personal beliefs about right and wrong, whereas cultural values are values accepted by religions or societies and reflect what is important in each context. Personal and cultural values may or may not align with moral values, which are typically seen as objectively valid and binding, regardless of whether they are accepted or not.</p> <p>Sources: Value Definition & Meaning - Merriam-Webster; Value Theory (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy); What are Values? - Ethics Sage; Moral Anti-Realism > Moral Objectivity and Moral Relativism (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy/Summer 2020 Edition)</p> <p>In an ethical sense, a value judgment can be said to be universal if it applies to all similarly situated individuals. Universalizability is commonly seen as a distinguishing feature of moral judgments—moral imperatives must be regarded as equally binding on everyone. The force of this principle, however, depends upon the generality of the judgments and the particularity of the situations to which they are applied.</p> <p>Source: Philosophical Dictionary: Ubermensch-Utilitarianism (philosophypages.com)</p>
12.	Well-being	<p>In a general philosophical sense, well-being describes what is non-instrumentally or ultimately good <i>for</i> a person. The question of what well-being consists in is of independent interest in moral philosophy, but it is of particular importance in the case of utilitarianism, according to which the only moral requirement is that well-being be maximized. In social sciences, well-being is seen as a broad and multifaceted construct that can essentially be divided into two large domains: objective and subjective well-being. Subjective well-being refers to a person’s self-reported “global assessment of all aspects” of their life. Objective well-being often refers to a set of societal circumstances generally captured by material, tangible, and quantitative indicators.</p> <p>Sources: Well-Being (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy); Well-Being Measurement – Lee Kum Sheung Center for Health and Happiness (harvard.edu); What is “wellbeing” — and why should we measure it? - ABC Religion & Ethics</p>

Appendix 2: Standardisation concepts in EU policy documents

The EU operates in a complex network of policies and regulations aimed at promoting harmonization and cooperation among member states. In this network, standards and standardisation processes play a vital role in ensuring interoperability, innovation, safety, sustainability, and efficiency in various sectors. As part of our broader study, this appendix provides an overview of how the analysed EU policy documents reference standards and standardisation. By examining the language and contexts in which standards are mentioned, we may gain additional insights into the role and significance of standardisation practices within the EU. Below, a list of the documents is provided along with the details on how the notions of standards and standardisation are represented in them.

1. The EU AI Act (The European Commission, 2021)

The term “standardisation” is mentioned 4 times in the document, whereas the term “standards” is mentioned 36 times, although not always in the context of standardisation. The contexts in which these terms are mentioned could be roughly classified as follows:

- **Importance of shaping standards on a global level:** on p. 5, it is stated that the proposal “strengthens significantly the Union’s role to help shape global norms and standards” and that “it provides the Union with a powerful basis to engage further with its external partners, including third countries, and at international fora on issues relating to AI”. A similar statement is also made on p. 6.
- **Importance of standardisation for compliance with requirements:** p. 6 states that “the proposal defines common mandatory requirements applicable to the design and development of certain AI systems before they are placed on the market that will be further operationalised through harmonised technical standards”. On p. 7, it is claimed that harmonised standards will assist providers and users in complying with the requirements for high-risk AI systems (high quality data, documentation and traceability, transparency, human oversight, accuracy and robustness). On p. 13, it is noted that standards or other technical specifications may provide precise technical solutions to achieve compliance with legal requirements for high-risk AI systems. P. 32 similarly states that “Standardisation should play a key role to provide technical solutions to providers to ensure compliance with this Regulation” and that “compliance with harmonised standards ... should be a means for providers to demonstrate conformity with the requirements of this Regulation.” P. 53 highlights that standards should be part of the quality management system “to ensure that the high-risk AI system complies with the requirements ...”. P. 78 states that the market surveillance authorities shall consider whether non-

compliance with AI system requirements (should it occur and not be corrected by the operator) stems from “shortcomings in the harmonised standards or common specifications referred to in Articles 40 and 41 conferring a presumption of conformity” or a failure to meet certain other requirements. P. 79 follows up on this: “Where the national measure is considered justified and the non-compliance of the AI system is attributed to shortcomings in the harmonised standards or common specifications referred to in Articles 40 and 41 of this Regulation, the Commission shall apply the procedure provided for in Article 11 of Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012”.

- Title III, Chapter 5 (“Standards, Conformity assessment, certificates, registration”) is in particular worth mentioning in relation to standardisation and conformity. In general, it states that high-risk systems “shall be presumed to be in conformity with the requirements set out in Chapter 2 of this Title, to the extent those standards cover those requirements” (p. 63), with Chapter 2 referring to the chapter that sets out the requirements for high-risk AI systems (e.g., compliance, transparency, data, documentation, etc.). Additionally, on p. 63, it is stated that “Where harmonised standards ... do not exist or where the Commission considers that the relevant harmonised standards are insufficient or that there is a need to address specific safety or fundamental right concerns, the Commission may, by means of implementing acts, adopt common specifications in respect of the requirements set out in Chapter 2 ...”. P. 64 specifies the conformity assessment procedures that the provider shall follow to demonstrate compliance of a high-risk system with Chapter 2 (namely, procedure based on internal control on the one hand and, on the other, procedure based on assessment of the quality management system and assessment of the technical documentation, with the involvement of a notified body). P. 65 states that where the manufacturer is enabled to opt out from a third-party conformity assessment by legal acts, “provided that that manufacturer has applied all harmonised standards covering all the relevant requirements, that manufacturer may make use of that option only if he has also applied harmonised standards”.
- **Importance of standardisation for managing high-risk AI systems:** on p. 20, the document stresses the importance of standards for EU core values regarding high-risk AI systems: “In order to ensure a consistent and high level of protection of public interests as regards health, safety and fundamental rights, common normative standards for all high-risk AI systems should be established. Those standards should be consistent with the Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union (the Charter) and should be non-discriminatory and in line with the Union’s international trade commitments”. Pp. 46–47 state that the risk management

system (for high-risk AI systems) “shall consist of a continuous iterative process run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic updating”, part of which is adoption of suitable measures. These measures “shall take into account the generally acknowledged state of the art, including as reflected in relevant harmonised standards or common specifications” (p. 47). P. 49 states that the systems should be developed with automatic recording of events (“logs”) capabilities which should be on while the system is operating and which “shall conform to recognised standards or common specifications”.

- **European standardisation bodies for AI:** p. 35 states that “in order to facilitate a smooth, effective and harmonised implementation of this Regulation a European Artificial Intelligence Board should be established. The Board should be responsible for a number of advisory tasks, including issuing opinions, recommendations, advice or guidance on matters related to the implementation of this Regulation, including on technical specifications or existing standards regarding the requirements established in this Regulation and providing advice to and assisting the Commission on specific questions related to artificial intelligence”. On p. 51, it is highlighted that “notified bodies shall participate in coordination activities as referred to in Article 38 [the conformity assessment procedures of AI systems]. They shall also take part directly or be represented in European standardisation organisations, or ensure that they are aware and up to date in respect of relevant standards”. Then, p. 73 states that “When providing advice and assistance to the Commission ... the Board shall [among other things] ... issue opinions, recommendations or written contributions on matters related to the implementation of this Regulation, in particular (i) on technical specifications or existing standards regarding the requirements ... , (ii) on the use of harmonised standards or common specifications ... , (iii) on the preparation of guidance documents ...”. Finally, “Member States shall ensure that ... national competent authorities shall have a sufficient number of personnel permanently available whose competences and expertise shall include an in-depth understanding of artificial intelligence technologies, data and data computing, fundamental rights, health and safety risks and knowledge of existing standards and legal requirements” (p. 73).

2. Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education et al., 2015)

While the term “standardisation” is not present in the document, it mentions the related terms “standard” or “standards” 60 times, mostly in relation to quality assurance in higher education.

However, many of those mentions are only there to set out a particular standard⁶ rather than to convey a general strategic perspective of on standardisation. For this reason, the focus here is placed on those instances of the term that are presented in a certain context.

According to the description of the scope and concepts in the document,

The ESG are a set of standards and guidelines for internal and external quality assurance in higher education. The ESG are not standards for quality, nor do they prescribe how the quality assurance processes are implemented, but they provide guidance, covering the areas which are vital for successful quality provision and learning environments in higher education. The ESG should be considered in a broader context that also includes qualifications frameworks, ECTS and diploma supplement that also contribute to promoting the transparency and mutual trust in higher education in the EHEA [European Higher Education Area]. (p. 4)

According to the Commission, the ESG need to be “reasonable generic”, given that acceptance of standards is important for fostering common understanding of quality assurance in the European higher education (p. 6). The document also divides the standards for quality assurance into three parts—internal quality assurance, external quality assurance, and quality assurance agencies—with the three parts being “intrinsically interlinked and together form the basis for a European quality assurance framework” (p. 7). In general, the ESG are meant to set out “agreed and accepted practice for quality assurance in higher education in the EHEA” that should “be taken account of and adhered to by those concerned, in all types of higher education provision” (p. 7).

The rest of the document puts forth particular standards supplemented with guidelines that explain why the standard is important and how it may be implemented. The document also contains an annex, which summarizes the list of standards (pp. 21–23).

3. An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market (The European Commission, 2022a)

This document mentions “standardisation” 7 times, “standard” 23 times, and “standards” 13 times. Since standardisation is the key focus of the document, most of the mentions of the term relate to the central ideas raised in it. Microsoft Copilot provides the following summary of the document:⁷

⁶ For example: “**Standard:** Institutions should consistently apply pre-defined and published regulations covering all phases of the student “life cycle”, e.g. student admission, progression, recognition and certification” (p. 10; emphasis added).

⁷ Generated using the prompt “Provide a comprehensive summary of ‘An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market’ that is at least 10 sentences long” in the “Precise” conversation mode.

“‘An EU Strategy on Standardisation: Setting Global Standards in Support of a Resilient, Green and Digital EU Single Market’ is a strategic document from the European Commission that aims to strengthen the EU’s global competitiveness and enable a resilient, green, and digital economy.

The strategy recognizes that standards are at the core of the EU single market and have delivered great benefits for companies and consumers. Over the last 30 years, the European Standardisation System has delivered more than 3600 harmonised standards, promoting interoperability, safety, and environmental protection.

However, the strategy also acknowledges that many third countries are taking an assertive stance to standardisation, providing their industries with a competitive edge. This has implications for Europe’s competitiveness, technological sovereignty, and ability to reduce dependencies.

The strategy proposes that European standardisation needs to become more agile, flexible, and focused to anticipate standardisation needs. It also needs to respond to an increasingly rapid innovation pace and deliver standards fast, while preserving high-quality outputs.

The strategy identifies that often private and non-European industry-led consortia are leaner and faster in developing standards. In particular, in new and emerging technologies, the European standardisation system often fails to deliver in a timely manner.

The strategy proposes a set of actions to put standards back at the core of a resilient, green, and digital EU single market and to strengthen the global role of the European standardisation system. It aims to anticipate, prioritise and address standardisation needs in strategic areas and improve the governance and integrity of the European standardisation system.”

A close look at the use of the standards-related terms in the document reveals that the summary presented above captures virtually all contexts relevant to the instances of their usage.

4. Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe’s Recovery (The European Commission, 2021b)

This document mentions “standardisation” 7 times, “standard” 3 times, and “standards” 13 times. The contexts in which these terms are mentioned could be categorized as follows:

- **Addressing product shortages:** standardisation is mentioned as a mechanism for addressing critical product shortages by speeding up product availability and reinforcing public procurement cooperation (p. 7).
- **Benefits for companies and consumers:** the document mentions that the European goods standards have benefited companies and consumers by increasing “quality and safety,

improving transparency, reducing costs and opening up markets for businesses” (p. 8). Similarly, it states that laying down technical requirements—e.g., levels of quality, performance, interoperability, environmental protection, protection of health or safety—through standardisation “can increase consumer confidence”, “further integrate European service markets”, and “overcome barriers linked to multiple national certification requirements” (p. 8). Moreover, harmonised standards are stated to have the potential benefits to “to facilitate cross-border activities, market potential and opening and overall economic benefit, including for SMEs and women entrepreneurs...” (p. 8).

- **Global leadership in standard-setting:** the document also stresses the importance of standard-setting for global leadership in technologies and for interoperability, stating that “global convergence on the same international standards helps reduce adaptation costs and strengthens EU and global value chains” (p. 14). It also strongly emphasises that EU industries need European and international standards for their resilience and competitiveness (p. 15).
- **The twin digital and green transition:** the document states that in the context of standardisation particular attention needs to be paid to the twin green and digital transition, which is identified as a key area (p. 15).
- **Green recovery:** the Commission seeks to pair green investments with the development of new standards for green finance to support the financing of a green recovery. This is done through the preparation of “Renewed Sustainable Finance Strategy” and a legislative initiative on sustainable corporate governance providing for due diligence by companies (p. 18).

5. ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market (The European Commission, 2016)

In total, this document contains 78 mentions of “standardisation”, 75 mentions of “standards”, and 30 mentions of “standard”. Due to the fact that the relevant terms are mentioned extensively on every page of the document, providing an outline of their usage contexts would be tantamount to summarizing the entire document. Therefore, one may consider the following summary of the key points by Microsoft Copilot:⁸

“The document ‘ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market’ is a key policy document of the European Commission. It outlines the importance of Information and

⁸ Generated using the prompt “Provide a comprehensive summary of ‘ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market’ that is at least 10 sentences long” in the “Precise” conversation mode.

Communication Technology (ICT) standards for achieving interoperability of new technologies, and the significant benefits they can bring to both industry and consumers.

The document emphasizes that ICT standards help ICT markets remain open and allow consumers the widest choice of products. It also highlights the EU's role in ICT standardisation, stating that standardisation is an essential component of industrial competitiveness.

The document mentions that many of the most commonly used ICT technical specifications are produced by forums and consortiums that have become leading ICT standards development bodies. It also explains that the Commission financially supports the work of the 3 European standardisation organisations: ETSI, CEN, and CENELEC.

The document underscores the importance of having common ICT standards to ensure that European industries are at the forefront of developing and exploiting ICT technologies. These standards ensure interoperability and guarantee that such technologies work smoothly and reliably together.

Finally, the document proposes to focus standard-setting resources and communities on 5 priority areas: 5G, Internet of Things, cloud computing, cybersecurity, and data technologies. These areas are considered essential for wider EU competitiveness and can accelerate digitisation, having an immediate impact on competitiveness in domains such as eHealth, intelligent transport systems, connected/automated vehicles, smart homes and cities, and advanced manufacturing.”

6. The 2024 Annual Union Work Programme for European Standardisation (The European Commission, 2024)

This document mentions “standardisation” 58 times, “standards” 140 times, and “standard” 16 times. Similar to the “ICT Standardisation Priorities for the Digital Single Market” covered above, it may be difficult to present the use cases of these terms without summarizing the entire document. However, it is noteworthy that most of the space in this document is dedicated to the table that lists and describes particular actions (72 in total) for the development and revision of European standards or European standardisation deliverables supporting the resilience of European industry. But if we focus on the introductory parts of the document, we can find the following strategic outlooks:

- **The general purpose:** “The Notice was drawn up to specifically support EU policies and legislation with the objective of contributing to a green, digital and resilient single market as well as the EU’s international objectives” (p. 1). Moreover, “Standards support EU policies to ensure that EU products and services are competitive worldwide and reflect state-of-the-art safety, security, health, social and environmental considerations. In addition, they are an important tool for research, development and innovation valorisation by demonstrating proof

of concept and leveraging the roll-out of completely new industrial value chains in the green and digital areas” (p. 1).

- **Global partnerships:** the document also mentions cooperation on standardisation with Japan, South Korea, and Singapore by implementing digital partnerships in the context of the EU-US Trade and Technology Council and within G7/G20 groups (p. 1). Additionally, “The Commission will promote [international] cooperation and exchange of information on standardisation ... as an essential part of the chapter on technical barriers to trade and good regulatory practices in every free trade agreement it negotiates” and “will continue dialogue with other countries to explore possible areas of cooperation on global challenges” (p. 1).
- **Promoting EU’s global leadership in standardisation:** it is stated that the annex to the “Annual Union Work Programme”—the table with a list of particular actions for developing European standards—presents standardisation deliverables that “are necessary and suitable for the support of EU legislation and policies, and thereby strengthen the EU’s leading role in setting global standards” (p. 1).
- **Strategic priorities:** The document contains a list of priority deliverables that “support critical EU policies in achieving a green, digital and resilient single market and deserve particular attention from the European standardisation system, including fast-track deliverables” (p. 1). The following areas are identified as policy priorities: 1. Technologies for European high-performance computing and European quantum communication infrastructure; 2. Critical raw materials – recycling of permanent magnets and exploration, extraction, refining and recycling of critical raw materials; 3. EU Trusted Data Framework; 4. European Digital Identity framework; 5. Ecodesign of air-to-air conditioning and heat pumps; 6. Cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements; 7. Hydrogen technologies and components; 8. Electric vehicle charging infrastructure (p. 2).